

IUTAM

IUTAM SYMPOSIUM

Particles, Drops and Bubbles in stratified Environments

Program and Book of Abstracts

4 - 6 July 2022 - Toulouse (France)

	Monday 4th		Tuesday 5th		Wednesday 6th
8h30	Welcome				
9h00	Introduction	9h00	T10 - Lohse	9h00	T17 - Zhang J.
9h15	Talk 1 - Le Gal	9h30	T11 - Ragavendiran	9h30	T18 - Fouxon
9h45	T2 - Voisin	10h00	PT #3 - Clercx	10h00	PT #5 - Hanazaki
10h15	T3 - Mehaddi				
10h45	Break	10h45	Break	10h45	Break
11h15	T4 - Roy	11h15	T12 - Boetti M.	11h15	T19 - Patibandla
11h45	Plenary Talk #1 - Ardekani	11h45	T13 - Zhang X. M.	11h45	T20 - Dabiri
		12h15	T14 - Christin	12h15	T21 - Mercier
12h30	Lunch	12h45	Lunch	12h45	Lunch
14h00	PT #2 - Landeau	14h15	PT #4 - Truscott	14h15	PT #6 - Prairie
14h45	T5 - Saifi	15h00	T15 - Darvenne	15h00	T22 - McLaughlin
15h15	T6 - Kriaa	15h30	T16 - Ratul	15h30	T23 - Mrokowska
15h45	Break	16h00	Break	16h00	Break
16h15	T7 - Kuppa	16h15	Visit of IMFT Laboratories	16h30	T24 - Mingotti
16h45	T8 - Li			17h00	PT #7 - Blanchette
17h15	T9 - Lingyun	17h30	End of visit		
17h45	going to Emulation	18h00	going to Les Abattoirs	17h45	closing discussions
18h30	Ice-breaker cocktail	18h30	Museum visit	18h45	end
		20h00	Gala dinner		

Hybrid comments

TIME ZONE	DT (h)	WHEN..
US west	-9	late afternoon
US east	-6	afternoon
India	5.5	morning
Japan	8	early morning

NOTES

7 Plenary TALKS (45min)
24 Talks (30min)
31 TOTAL

hybrid sessions

IUTAM Chairman: Jacques Magnaudet

IUTAM co-Chair: Arezoo M. Ardekani

Local Organizing Committee (IMFT):

Jacques Magnaudet, Matthieu Mercier, Muriel Sabater, Sylvie Senny

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- François Blanchette, University California Merced (USA)
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- Jennifer Prairie, University of San Diego (USA)
- Atila Pantaleao Silva Freire, Federal University Rio de Janeiro (Brazil), IUTAM representative

> Monday, July 4th

8h30	Welcome
9h00	Introduction
9h15	Talk 1 - Le Gal
9h45	T2 - Voisin - <i>(Hybrid session)</i>
10h15	T3 - Mehaddi
10h45	Break
11h15	T4 - Roy - <i>(Hybrid session)</i>
11h45	Plenary Talk #1 - Ardekani
12h30	Lunch
14h00	Plenary Talk #2 - Landeau
14h45	T5 - Aadil
15h15	T6 - Kriaa
15h45	Break
16h15	T7 - Kuppa
16h45	T8 - Li - <i>(Hybrid session)</i>
17h15	T9 - Lingyun - <i>(Hybrid session)</i>
17h45	Going to Emulation
18h30	Ice-breaker cocktail

SWIMMING OF A LUDION IN A STRATIFIED SEA

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Topic(s): swimmers

Key words: Descartes diver, resonance, added mass and friction, gravity waves

Abstract:

We describe and model experimental results on the dynamics of a "ludion" - a neutrally buoyant body - immersed in a layer of stably stratified salt water. By oscillating a piston inside a cylinder communicating with a vessel containing the stably stratified layer of salt water, it is easy to periodically vary the hydrostatic pressure of the fluid. The ludion or Cartesian diver, initially positioned at its equilibrium height and free to move horizontally, can then oscillate vertically when forced by the pressure oscillations. Depending on the ratio of the forcing frequency to the Brunt-Väisälä frequency of the stratified fluid, the ludion can emit its own internal gravity waves that we measure by a classical Particle Image Velocimetry technique. Our experimental results describe first the resonance of the vertical motions of the ludion when excited at different frequencies. A theoretical oscillator model is then derived taking into account added mass and added friction coefficients and its predictions are compared to the experimental data. Then, for the larger oscillation amplitudes, we observe and describe a bifurcation towards free horizontal motions (cf. Fig. 1). Although the internal gravity wave frequencies are affected by the Doppler shift induced by the horizontal displacement velocities, it seems that, contrary to surface waves associated with Couder walkers [1] they are not the cause of the horizontal swimming. This does not however, exclude possible interactions between the ludion and internal gravity waves and possible hydrodynamic quantum analogies to be explored in the future.

Figure 1: Trajectory of the ludion swimming for 1 hour in a cubic box. Forcing frequency $\omega = 1.38 \text{ rad/s}$ and stratification Brunt-Väisälä frequency $N = 1.61 \text{ rad/s}$.

References

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Added mass in the presence of density stratification

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Topic(s): Particles; other.

Key words: Added mass; internal waves; internal tide; buoyancy oscillations.

Abstract:

Added mass represents the additional inertia experienced by a body as it moves through a fluid, owing to the flow that this motion generates within the fluid. Being involved in the energy and impulse of the fluid, together with the dipole strength of the body and the hydrodynamic force exerted on it, added mass characterizes the flow both globally and locally. When the fluid can support the propagation of waves, inertial added mass, a real number at any given frequency, is complemented by an imaginary part associated with wave drag.

The concept of added mass is extended to stratified fluids and internal gravity waves. The stratification is assumed uniform, the fluid inviscid, the waves linear and the Boussinesq approximation valid. The added mass coefficients of two oscillating bodies, an elliptic cylinder in two dimensions and a spheroid of vertical axis in three dimensions, are determined based on results obtained with the boundary integral method [1]. Fourier inversion allows the frequency variations of the coefficients to be interpreted as a new memory integral for the force exerted on the body, with kernel represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Memory kernel for the oscillations either horizontal (left) or vertical (right) of a spheroid of vertical axis, axial length $2b$, transverse diameter $2a$ and aspect ratio $\varepsilon = b/a$, as a function of time t . The buoyancy period is denoted as T , and the added mass coefficients of the spheroid in the absence of stratification as $C_{x,z}^{\infty}$.

Two applications are discussed: the wave energy, of particular importance for the internal tide, in whose context it is known as conversion rate [2]; and buoyancy oscillations, namely the free oscillations by which a displaced body returns back to equilibrium, of particular importance for midwater floats [3, 4, 5, 6]. These theoretical results are compared to experiment for two types of buoyancy oscillations: those undergone by a sphere displaced from its neutral buoyancy level then released [7, 8, 9, 10]; and the oscillations of a ludion or Cartesian diver [11]. The influence of viscosity at high Stokes number is discussed, together with the relation to measurements of added mass by the impulse response method (see [12, 13] and the references therein).

References

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Theoretical study of a particle moving in a stratified rotating fluid

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Stratification, sphere, rotation

Abstract:

When a particle is immersed in a viscous stratified rotating fluid, it undergoes inertial perturbations due to both the fluid rotation and to the advection and diffusion of the stratifying agent. The objective of this study is to investigate how the effects of inertia due to stratification and rotation mix. Should they simply be added together in a linear fashion? Does one vanish in favour of the second when the latter dominates? This question is important because it has implications in the analysis of turbulent stratified flows loaded with particles. In addition to providing answers at the fundamental scale, this problem has also practical applications in various fields such as centrifugation in the presence of a thermal or a salinity gradient, or the swimming of microorganisms or the transport of particles in oceans subjected to the Coriolis force induced by the rotation of the Earth or rotation due to typhoons or tornadoes, to name but a few. The drag experienced by particles in rotating fluid has been analysed by several authors, in the case of homogenous ambient fluid. One of the pioneering researchers on that problem is Childress [1]. However, there are very few studies that considered particles in a rotating stratified fluid. For instance, Mason [2] and Johnson & Llewellyn Smith [3] have respectively carried out an experimental and a theoretical study devoted to the large Reynolds number behaviour. For the case of small Reynolds number behaviour, we can quote Graebel [4] who studied the motion of a cylinder moving horizontally in rotating non-diffusive stratified fluid. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that considered finite-dimensional bodies in a rotating stratified ambient at low Reynolds number.

To compute the resistive forces experienced by the particle, Navier-Stokes equations are written in the rotating frame that translates with the particle. Using matched asymptotic method, this force has been obtained in an integral form that involves three different length scales namely the stratification length scale, the Oseen length scale (based on slip velocity) and the Ekman length scale (based on the ambient rotation). The asymptotic behaviours of this integral have been analysed in details. In particular, when stratification dominates, it has been found that, the particle experiences a lift force f_l . The expression of this force reads as

$$\frac{f_l}{6\pi\rho_\infty\nu au} \approx 1.0166 \frac{Ta}{\text{Ri}^{1/4}\text{Pe}^{1/4}} \quad \text{in the viscous-diffusive regime} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{f_l}{6\pi\rho_\infty\nu au} \approx 1.0266 \frac{Ta}{\text{Ri}^{1/3}} \quad \text{in the viscous-advective regime} \quad (2)$$

where a is the particle radius, u its velocity, ρ_∞ is a reference density, ν is the viscosity, $Ta = a^2\Omega/\nu$ is the Taylor number, Ω is the rotation rate, $Pr = \nu/\kappa$ is the Prandtl number, κ is the diffusivity, $Ri = a^3N^2/(u\nu)$ is the Richardson number and N is the Brunt Vaisala frequency that characterises the ambient stratification. The expression of this force can be expressed in a more compact form using the lift coefficient $C_l = f_l/(1/2\rho_\infty u^2 \pi a^2)$ as $C_l \approx 12 \Omega \ell / u = 12 \text{Ro}^{-1}$, where Ro is the Rossby number, u is the particle velocity, Ω is the rotation rate and ℓ is a stratification length scale. This length scale is $\ell = \ell_S = (\nu\kappa/N^2)^{1/4}$ in the diffusive regime and $\ell = \ell_a = (u\nu/N^2)^{1/3}$ in the advective regime. By inspecting the problems of a particle immersed in a rotating flow or in a simple shear flow, it appears that they share common characteristics. This similarity is related to the structure of the problem. From this observation, we can conjecture that the lift that would experience a particle in a stratified shear flow with a shear rate s would be $C_l \propto s\ell/u$ where the length scale ℓ would depend on the flow regime, similarly to the rotating case.

References

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Drag and deformation of a drop settling in a linearly stratified fluid

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Topic(s): Drops/bubbles, stratified fluids.

Key words: settling particle, drop deformation.

Abstract:

A translating spherical drop is a solution of the Stokes equations, satisfying the stress boundary conditions exactly at the spherical interface [1]. Recently Shaik & Ardekani [2] considered an extension of this classical problem - the drag on a translating drop in a linearly density-stratified fluid. In the Stokesian limit, a stratification screening length exists based on the balance of viscous and buoyancy forces. Similar to other problems of this nature (for instance, Saffman's calculation of the inertial lift on a spherical particle in a simple shear flow [3] and Childress' calculation of inertial correction to the drag for axial motion of a sphere in a rotating fluid [4]), the solution in the outer region, exterior to the screening length, is sufficient to calculate the first-order correction to the Stokesian drag in a homogeneous ambient. The outer region solution appears as a uniform flow on scales small compared to the aforementioned stratification screening length, and the flow in the inner region thus remains identical to that in a homogeneous ambient, the well-known Hadamard–Rybczynski flow field, albeit with an altered amplitude. As a result, a translating spherical drop remains undeformed even in a background stratification, and the authors above found an enhancement of the drag on this spherical drop due to the background stratification. The result is consistent with those of previous calculations for rigid spheres, across a range of asymptotic regimes, all of which predict a stratification-induced drag enhancement. We revisit this problem and calculate the flow field in the inner region, accounting for buoyancy effects. The buoyancy forcing results in a dipolar flow field having the character of a uniaxial extension. This deforms the drop into a prolate shape, allowing for the possibility of a reduced drag. We demarcate regions of enhanced and reduced drag in an appropriate parameter space.

(a) Streamlines for a translating drop in a quiescent homogeneous fluid - the Hadamard–Rybczynski solution

(b) The $\mathcal{O}(Ri_v)$ correction to the streamlines in a linearly density-stratified fluid

Figure 1: Streamline patterns for a translating drop in a quiescent fluid

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Settling and swimming in density stratified fluids

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Topic(s): Particles, drops/bubbles, swimmers, miscible stratified fluids.

Key words: linear density stratification, hydrodynamic interaction, settling, swimming

Abstract:

Density variations due to temperature or salinity variations greatly influence the flow around and the sedimentation of objects such as rigid/porous particles, drops/bubbles, and micro/small organisms in the atmosphere, oceans, and lakes. Density stratification hampers the vertical flow and substantially affects the sedimentation of an isolated object, the hydrodynamic interactions between a pair, and the collective behavior of suspensions in various ways depending on the relative magnitude of stratification, inertia (advection), and viscous (diffusion) effects. In this talk I will discuss these effects and elicits the hydrodynamic mechanisms behind some commonly observed fluid-particle transport phenomena in stratified fluids. For example, We show that a swimmer can experience change of stability based on the relative importance of the above-mentioned effects.

Figure 1: Inertial effects which make pullers unstable but stabilize pushers, while stratification effects which make pushers

unstable but stabilize pullers.

References

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Instability, mixing and drop fragmentation during a giant planetary impact

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Topic(s): drops/bubbles, miscible (unstably) stratified fluids.

Key words: liquid impact, liquid fragmentation, turbulent entrainment, drop size, Earth formation.

Abstract:

Liquid impact and fragmentation occurred on a massive scale during the formation of the Earth, when high-energy planetary collisions built up its mass. Following each impact, the metallic core of the impactor fragmented into drops inside Earth's mantle. The size of the metal drops and their degree of mixing with Earth's mantle are unknown. Yet, they controlled the efficiency of chemical transfers, and hence the composition of Earth's interior.

We investigate the fluid dynamics of planetary collisions using laboratory experiments. In liquid impacts (Fig.1, top), we reproduce the crater observed in numerical simulations of planetary impacts [1]. During the opening of the crater, we observe Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities [2]. At the end of the impact process, the volume of target liquid that is entrained and mixed with the impacting liquid is controlled by the ratio between the impactor inertia and its buoyancy [1]. We then investigate the fragmentation of a liquid volume into an immiscible liquid (Fig.1, bottom). We obtain scaling laws for the mean drop size as a function of the Weber number, which is the ratio of inertia to surface tension. These scalings agree with theoretical predictions in a turbulent flow [3]. Applying our results to Earth formation, we predict the efficiency of chemical transfers between the impactor's metal and Earth's mantle following a planetary collision.

Figure 1: (Top) Impact of a volume of salt solution into a water pool to model the impacts that formed the Earth. (Bottom) Fragmentation of a liquid into a lighter immiscible liquid to model the fragmentation of liquid metal into Earth's mantle.

References

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EFFECT OF OUTER VISCOSITY AND SURFACE TENSION GRADIENTS ON COALESCENCE OF A DROP

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Topic(s): drops/bubbles, immiscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Coalescence of drops, Marangoni effect, Surface tension gradient.

Abstract:

The Marangoni Effect is a phenomenon taking place at the interface of two fluids which causes movement of interface and consequently drag fluid near the interface along with it, resulting in a flow from lower surface tension region towards higher surface tension region. The coalescence of drops is a naturally occurring phenomenon with various industrial applications. Few such examples in this context are raindrop formations, ocean mist and emulsions. Another application is found in microfluidic devices and micro-scale chemical synthesis where manipulation of liquid drops is often required.

In this work we have studied the coalescence of a millimeter sized drop on a pool of liquid in the presence of a surrounding viscous liquid, wherein the drop has a different surface tension than the pool. The effect of outer fluid viscosity on the coalescence dynamics and Marangoni effects are examined. Here we have employed a 2D axisymmetric numerical model to investigate the drop merger dynamics using open source code *Basilisk*[1], wherein liquid pool is modelled as water, and the surroundings are modelled as silicone oils of different viscosities. The drop is modelled as a mixture of ethylene glycol(EG) and water where concentration of ethylene glycol is varied to study the extent of Marangoni effect. The drop is placed over the top of reservoir as shown in figure 1(a), where C_1 is concentration of EG in drop and C_0 is concentration of EG in liquid pool. The results, as shown by figure 1(b), indicate merger time of the drop at different surface concentration gradient for varying viscosity ratio, $\mu_r = \mu_d/\mu_o$, where μ_d and μ_o are viscosities of the drop and surrounding fluid respectively. It is observed that total coalescence is prominent in the cases studied.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic diagram of the drop placed over a reservoir; (b) Plot showing merger times of drop into the pool for different concentration where, C_1 is concentration of Ethylene Glycol, while $C_0 = 0$ in all cases

References

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Iron snow in planetary interiors: inert and reactive particle clouds settling in still and rotating environments

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Talk 6

Topic: particles.

Key words: particle clouds, turbulent entrainment, rotating flows, two-way coupling.

Abstract:

Small telluric planets like Mercury or Ganymede – a natural satellite of Jupiter – generate their own magnetic field, likely through dynamo action inside an iron-rich liquid core. The motions generating the dynamo would originate from solid iron snow flakes falling from the periphery to the centre of the liquid core. Understanding the dynamo of such planets requires to model the snow before and during melting [1], and to determine whether the collective dynamics of snow flakes can produce a macroscopic flow nourishing the dynamo. Experimentally, we firstly model the snow thanks to spherical glass beads, released with no impulse in still fresh water. This enables to study the turbulence produced by the falling particles, as well as the feedback of turbulence on the particles' trajectories. Photographs are simultaneously taken by two cameras, which enables to perform a Lagrangian tracking of particles, and to quantify the turbulent flow using PIV or LIF (see figure 1a). Finally, the setup is mounted on a rotating table to account for planetary rotation on the particles' dynamics.

In the canonical framework of Morton [2], the particle clouds' dynamics is studied by performing systematic experiments for one same initial density anomaly, varying two parameters: the radius of particles and the angular velocity of the rotating table. Modifying the radius of particles notably modifies the ratio of particle-to-fluid inertia – the Rouse number – which plays a major role in the clouds' dynamics. In a still environment, the collective settling of particles and their inertial coupling with the fluid contribute to enhancing the entrainment capacity of clouds. Subsequently, the cloud kinematics undergoes a transition as particles decouple from turbulent eddies (see figure 1a). Rotation, however, inhibits particulate effects which no longer enhance the entrainment. It introduces a new transition as clouds roll around the vertical axis of rotation and become vortical columnar flows. These diverse transitions separate different regimes of particles' settling, some of which may produce a large scale turbulent flow inside a planet.

In an upgraded version of our experimental approach, glass beads are replaced by dissolving crystals of salt or sugar to model melting of the snow flakes. This enables to assess the influence of dissolution on sedimentation and on the underlying convective motions driven by buoyancy in the fluid.

Experiments constitute a solid benchmark to validate numerical methods whose aim is to model such particulate flows at a planetary scale. Numerical simulations are performed with Basilisk [3] (see figure 1b) using a one-fluid model (i.e. particles behave as tracers with an additional constant velocity in the direction of gravity) with the geometry of experiments, enabling to compare numerical and experimental results.

Figure 1: (a) Decoupling between turbulence (in orange) and particles of mean radius $\bar{r}_p = 64\mu\text{m}$ (in white) in a still environment. (b) Adaptive mesh coloured with the field of particle concentration in a falling cloud modelled with Basilisk.

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Fluid Mechanics of Emulsification through cavitation in a water-in-oil system

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Topic(s): drops/bubbles.

Key words: Fragmentation, Cavitation, Emulsions.

Abstract:

Ultrasonic emulsification is a well-established method for the generation of microemulsions. The application of intense acoustic waves results in the nucleation of cavitation bubbles, which in turn cause through their oscillations and interaction with the suspended phase to the fragmentation of droplets into smaller scales. Owing to the practical relevance, research interest on cavitation-induced emulsification has been primarily centred on the final size of the microemulsions but less on understanding the complex fluid mechanics. Here we shed light on the physics of cavitation-based emulsification by studying the interaction between a single laser-induced cavitation bubble and a similar sized water droplet. Both the bubble and the drop are submerged in silicon oil using high-speed imaging. The interactions occur over multiple cycles of bubble expansion and collapse with jetting into the droplet. As a large number of smaller droplets inside and around the parent droplet are formed. Three distinct pathways for the formation of oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions are identified: crown jetting, lamella jetting and induced jetting. The formation of these internal O/W emulsions is usually a combination of either two or all the three identified pathways. Additionally, we find that the process of internal emulsification is accompanied by the formation of an outer water-in-oil emulsions.

Figure 1: Overview of the microemulsification process when a cavitation bubble of maximum diameter interacts $1283\mu\text{m}$ interacts with a water droplet. The initial droplet diameter is $671\mu\text{m}$ and the centre-to-centre distance between the droplet and the bubble is $525\mu\text{m}$.

Marangoni instabilities of drops of different viscosities in stratified liquids

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Topic(s): drops, swimmers, miscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Marangoni convection, absolute/convection instability, stratified flows.

Abstract: A drop immersed in a continuously stratified liquid often experiences Marangoni flow, due to the thermal/solute gradient which is responsible for the stratification. This system is one of the most basic examples where Marangoni (surface tension forces) competes with Rayleigh (gravity). Inspired by the previous works [1, 2], we further explore the phase space of such a system by systematically varying the concentration gradient, the drop size and the drop viscosity.

Linear stratifications of ethanol on top of water are prepared by a modified two-bucket method [3]. Silicone oil is used as it is immiscible with the stratified liquid and quite robust to impurities. Drops with different radius R and viscosity μ' are released in liquids with different stratifications, represented by the gradient of ethanol weight fractions dw/dy , to explore the phase space of the system. It is found that when the drop is small, it only levitates in the stratified liquid. Upon increasing its size, the drop levitates at a lower position, until above a critical size R_{cr} , it starts to bounce. Fig. 1(a) shows the temporal evolution of the 100 cSt drops' height in a stratified liquid with gradient $dw/dy \approx 40 \text{ m}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1(b)). This transition from levitating to bouncing indicates an oscillatory instability of the Marangoni flow. Fig. 1(c) shows the streamlines around a levitating 100 cSt drop ($R = 143 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$).

We further explain the onset of this Marangoni instability in more detail. It was found that, for low viscosity drops, the instability is triggered when the Marangoni advection is too strong for diffusion to restore the concentration field around the drop. The instability criterion is found to be $Ma/Ra^{1/2} > s$ (see the red line in Fig. 1(d)), where s is a constant to be determined, $Ma = V_M R/D$ and $Ra = -d\rho/dy \cdot gR^4/(\mu D)$. For high viscosity drops, the instability is triggered when the gravitational effect is too strong so that the viscous stress cannot maintain a stable Marangoni flow. The instability criterion is found to be $Ra/Ma > c$, where c is a constant that depends on the viscosity of the drop. See the blue lines in Fig. 1(d). Subsequently, a unifying scaling theory that includes both instability criteria for drops of different viscosities is developed. The transition between the two situations is found to be controlled by two length scales: the drop radius R and the boundary layer thickness δ of the Marangoni flow around the drop. The instability is dominated by diffusion when $\delta < R$ and by viscosity when $R < \delta$. The experimental results for various drops of different viscosities can well be described with this unifying scaling theory, see Fig. 1(d). Our theoretical description thus provides a unifying view of physicochemical hydrodynamic problems in which the Marangoni stress is competing with a stable stratification.

Figure 1: Levitating and bouncing drops in a linearly stratified mixture of ethanol (top) and water (bottom). (a) Drops' height h as functions of time t for different drop radius R . They are all released at $t = 0$ s. Here $h = 0$ is the density matched position. The filled circles represent the relative size of the drops. (b) The ethanol weight fraction w at the corresponding heights: $dw/dy \approx 40 \text{ m}^{-1}$. (c) Streamlines around a levitating drop ($R = 143 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$) in a concentration gradient $dw/dy \approx 10 \text{ m}^{-1}$. The red arrows indicate the flow directions. (d) Phase diagram of the instability thresholds for different drop viscosities.

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Critical density triplets for the arrestment of a sphere falling in a sharply stratified fluid

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids

Key words: Stratified fluid, Sedimentation, Levitation.

Abstract:

We study the motion of a rigid sphere falling in a two-layer stratified fluid under the action of gravity in the potential flow regime. Experiments at a moderate Reynolds number of approximately 20 to 450 indicate that a sphere with the precise critical density, higher than the bottom layer density, can display behaviors such as bounce or arrestment after crossing the interface. We experimentally and numerically demonstrate that such a critical sphere density decreases as the fluid density transition layer thickness increases and increases linearly as the bottom fluid density increases with a fixed top fluid density. Additionally, we documented the dependence of prolonged settling time on the fluid and sphere densities.

> Ice breaker cocktail **Emulation Nautique** at 18 h 30
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5 min walking from IMFT

> Tuesday, July 5th

9h00	T10 - Lohse
9h30	T11 - Ragavendiran
10h00	Plenary Talk #3 - Clercx
10h45	Break
11h15	T12 - Boetti M. - (Hybrid session)
11h45	T13 - Zhang X. M.
12h15	T14 - Christin
12h45	Lunch
14h15	Plenary Talk #4 - Truscott
15h00	T15 - Darvenne
15h30	T16 - Ratul
16h00	Break
16h15	Visit of IMFT Laboratories
17h30	End of visit
18h00	Going to Les Abattoirs
18h30	Museum visit
20h00	Gala dinner

BOUNCING OIL DROPLET IN A STRATIFIED LIQUID AND ITS SUDDEN DEATH

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Topic(s): Drops/bubbles, swimmers, stratified fluids.

Key words: Droplets, Marangoni flow, physicochemical hydrodynamics

Abstract: One of the most basic examples for a droplet far from physicochemical equilibrium is the one of an immiscible (oil) droplet (of radius R) in a concentration gradient of two other liquids (with density lighter respectively heavier than the oil droplet), see figure 1. The two control parameters reflecting the non-equilibrium situation are the Marangoni number Ma defined with the gradient of the surface tension, i.e., $\Delta\sigma = R\partial_z\sigma$, and the Rayleigh number Ra , defined with the gradient in density, $\Delta\rho = R\partial_z\rho$. For the case of Stokes flow (small Reynolds number) and zero density gradient, the resulting velocity and the concentration fields can be analytically calculated [1]. The former can be quantified by the Marangoni velocity V_M at the equator of the droplet or, in dimensionless form, the (Marangoni-)Peclet number $Pe_M = V_M R/D$. If large enough, i.e., for a large enough concentration gradient, this Marangoni flow can make the droplet jump upwards in the stratified density gradient, against gravity [2]!

In more detail, what happens is the following series of events, that we will describe for the concrete example of a silicon oil droplet in a stratified (fully miscible) mixture of water (bottom) and ethanol (top) with constant density gradient in between: First, the oil droplet sinks in the gradient region, trying to find its equilibrium position with respect to density. Ethanol-rich liquid is entrained downwards during this motion. This entrainment is enhanced by the Marangoni flow along the drop surface, from the ethanol-rich top (low surface tension) to the ethanol-poor bottom, leading to further entrainment of ethanol-rich liquid. As the droplet asymptotically approaches the density matched position, the self-enhancing Marangoni flow eventually overcomes the sinking-induced buoyancy jet. This positive feed-back leads to a linear instability and exponential growth of the Marangoni flow, which pushes the liquid around the drop downwards and thus the drop upwards, like a micro-swimmer in the pulling mode [3]. Once this Marangoni flow is dominant (typically after $\sim 60s$), the drop shoots upwards towards the low density region and the process can start over. Up to six hours of consecutive jumps have been observed. The process only comes to an end once the jumping droplet has sufficiently mixed the stratified liquid. The system can be seen as canonical example for the competition between Marangoni (surface tension forces) and Rayleigh (gravity). For more details we refer to ref. [2].

Figure 1. A sinking anise oil drop in a continuously stratified mixture of ethanol (top) and water (bottom), shown through shadowgraph and PIV image in (a) and the corresponding numerical simulation in (b). On the right of each of these figures, the velocity field is shown, both as color code and as stream lines (in the lab frame). On the left, in (a) a snapshot of the shadowgraph is shown and in (b) the ethanol concentration inside and outside the anise oil drop (also shown in the lab frame). The entrained ethanol-rich liquid, the self-enhancing Marangoni flow and the buoyancy jet are all visible in these images. Figures (a) and (b) refer to the situation of ref. [2].

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An oscillating bubble passing through the liquid-liquid interface

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Topic(s): Immiscible stratified fluids

Key words: rising bubble, liquid-liquid interface, high-speed imaging, stratified flow

Abstract:

A bubble rising in a tank of two immiscible liquids, water (lower liquid) and canola oil (upper liquid), has been studied experimentally. The bubble's three-dimensional motion is captured using two high-speed (MotionPro Y5 series) cameras at high frame rates. In addition, we have carried out the time-resolved particle image velocimetry (TR-PIV) measurements in canola oil. The Reynolds number (Re) defined based on equivalent diameter of bubble (d_{eq}) is varied by changing the size of bubble. Here, we characterize size, shape, and path of bubbles that go through the interface along with deformation of the liquid-liquid (l-l) interface. Bubble's terminal velocity (v_T) in the lower liquid is validated with previous studies [1, 2]. Bubble coming from the lower liquid either with zigzag or spiral path transitions to a straight trajectory when rising in the upper liquid. The bulging of the interface just after the bubble crossing is perhaps due to the influence of wake region left behind by the rising bubble in the lower liquid (see Fig.1). The bubble carries a part of lower liquid into upper liquid, as shown in Fig.2(b). An air bubble rising in canola oil after crossing the interface carries lower liquid along with it due to the recirculation region behind the bubble, as can be seen in the PIV measurements carried out behind a bubble rising in a single liquid only (see Fig.2 b and c).

Figure 1: Sequence (from left to right) of bubble of $d_{eq} \approx 13.8$ mm rising through liquid-liquid interface. The interval between frames $\Delta t \approx 56.25$ ms. Similar observations showed in literature [3]. The liquid-liquid interface initial position shown dash line in red color

Figure 2: (a) Comparison of bubble velocity with literatures. (b) Lower liquid pulled up by bubble ($d_{eq} \approx 10.3$ mm) after column breakup. (i) view of x-z plane (ii) view of y-z plane. (c) Streamlines are plotted on top of a velocity map v , with red to blue colormap in the range $-0.2 \leq v \leq 0.2$ of bubble rising in canola oil $d_{eq} \approx 10.1$ mm.

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ON DISPERSION, PREFERENTIAL CONCENTRATION AND SETTLING OF INERTIAL PARTICLES IN STRATIFIED TURBULENCE

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Topic(s): Particles, miscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Inertial particles, preferential concentration, stratified turbulence.

Abstract:

Our understanding of the dynamics of inertial particles in turbulent flows has increased considerably during the last few decades. In particular, our ability to track many individual particles in laboratory experiments has increased and gives access to Lagrangian statistics of those particles such as velocity and acceleration probability distribution functions and radial distribution functions as measure for particle clustering. Additionally, the availability of facilities and algorithms for large-scale computations of trajectories of millions of particles allowed us to explore, for example, phenomena like preferential concentration, settling processes, and high-quality Lagrangian statistics of heavy particles in turbulence. The main proportion of these studies focused on particle dynamics in homogeneous isotropic turbulence and consider mostly the case of heavy inertial particles, meaning that the particle density is much larger than the density of the fluid in which they are embedded, or passive tracers (behaving like fluid elements). In this contribution we will extend the scope and address two aspects relevant for environmental applications: 1) the dynamics of inertial particles in stratified turbulence [1] and in homogeneous shear turbulence [2], and 2) the role of the particle-to-fluid density ratio on the dynamics of inertial particles in (stratified) turbulence [3-5]. For example, we will discuss the role of the pressure gradient force and the Basset history force on vertical dispersion and settling processes, the impact of stratification and particle-to-fluid density ratio on preferential concentration, and non-trivial horizontal drift of settling particles in homogeneous shear turbulence.

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INERTIAL PARTICLES CROSSING A STRATIFIED TURBULENT/NON-TURBULENT INTERFACE

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids, turbulent/non-turbulent interface.

Keywords: inertial particles, stratified turbulence.

Abstract:

The motion of particles in turbulent stratified environments is relevant to many natural processes, i.e. oxygen regulation for ocean organisms by bubbles rising across the oceans thermocline [1, 2]. The dynamics of particles crossing stratified interfaces is rather peculiar, since they present a significant slow down while crossing the stratified region, as previous experiments already determined in quiescent flows [3, 4].

We then extend the study of this problem investigating particles moving in stratified turbulent/non-turbulent interface (STNTI) flow from both the experimental and the numerical perspectives. Lagrangian analysis offers valuable insights into the understanding of particles dynamics when the turbulence is strongly inhomogeneous and anisotropic due to the presence of the stratification [5, 6]. Hence we developed a new force model based on Ref. [4] and implemented it in DNS flows. The model, Eqs.1-2, takes into consideration the effect on particles due to fluid stratification for spheres crossing STNTIs.

$$\mathbf{F}_S = (\rho_c - \rho_f) V_c \mathbf{g} \quad (1)$$

being $\rho_c(t)$, V_c the density and volume of the fluid surrounding the sphere, dragged across isopycnals.

We parameterise the change of ρ_c according to the two-layer experimental observations [4] and modified for DNS with temperature variations:

$$\frac{d\rho_c}{dt} = \frac{\rho_f(t - \tau_{\text{cross}}) - \rho_c}{\tau_{\text{rec}}} \quad (2)$$

$\tau_{\text{cross}} = \beta Re^m a^2/\nu$ represents the temporal interval between the entrance into the interfacial layer and the exit from it, being $\beta = 140$, $m = -1.7$ empirical constants [3], Re , a and ν the particle Reynolds number, diameter and kinematic viscosity respectively. The recovery time, $\tau_{\text{rec}} = 13Re^{-1} a^2/\nu$, was formulated by [4] as the time needed by the particle to recover its settling velocity in the second layer after it reached the minimal velocity.

In Fig. 1.a is reported the scheme of the experiment and one of the DNSs setup while Fig. 1.b presents the numerical particles vertical velocity results using the new force model. To favour a qualitative comparison with simulations, the experimental results (3D-PTV) of particle velocity are reported as well. The main highlight of the experiment is the presence of the particles slow down in STNTIs. Moreover, we obtained plausible results from the model since it produces similar dynamics to the experiment.

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of particles falling/rising in the two-layer oscillating grid system. The location of the 3D-PTV control volume is marked as a small (red) volume. (b) Numerical particles vertical profiles (coordinates are normalised by the interface thickness h) of vertical velocity normalized by the settling velocity in the quiescent layer, v^* . Blue curves: mean velocity (continuous) and standard deviation (dotted); grey lines: single particle velocity. Arrow indicates the particles mean direction. The inset shows the experiment results.

Dynamics of neutrally buoyant particles in thermally stratified turbulent channel flows

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Topic(s): particles.

Key words: neutrally buoyant particles, stably stratified channel flow, particle dispersion.

Abstract:

Many industrial and geophysical flows, from heat exchangers to the atmosphere, are influenced by the presence of stable stratification. The ability to predict mixing and dispersion of particles in these situations is therefore of great importance. A Lagrangian perspective, focusing on the advection of neutrally buoyant or slightly inertial particles, is a natural approach to study mixing and dispersion. In unstratified turbulence, particles can move vertically under the influence of vortical structures (over unlimited distances), and large-scale vertical dispersion is relatively insensitive to small-scale molecular mixing. However, in stably stratified turbulence, work must be done against buoyancy forces to move particles in the vertical direction. Therefore, the particle motion is constrained to a smaller distance about its equilibrium level, and molecular diffusion may become important. However, the fundamental physics of the processes mentioned above is just partially understood, and deeper understanding is required.

The present work was devoted to a systematic phenomenological study on particle dispersion in wall-bounded stratified turbulence at a shear Reynolds number (which measures the importance of inertial forces compared to viscous forces) of $Re_\tau=1000$ and shear Richardson number (which measures the importance of buoyancy forces compared to inertial forces) $Ri_\tau=200$. In this condition, turbulence is sustained only near the wall boundaries, whereas non-turbulent wavy structures (internal gravity waves, IGW, see Figure 1a) were observed at the core of the channel [1]. A total of one million particles with a density equal to ($\rho_r=1$) or smaller than ($\rho_r=0.8$) the surrounding fluid were released into the stratified flow from eleven wall-normal locations. Pseudo-spectral direct numerical simulations coupled with a Lagrangian particle tracking method within the one-way coupling regime were employed for the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations and analysis of particle dynamics.

One of the main outcomes of this study suggests that particles in the near-wall region are frequently entrained within vortical structures of turbulence (see the particle trajectory in Figure 1c). However, in the channel centre, due to the presence of IGW, the movements of particles in the wall-normal and spanwise directions are suppressed (see the particle trajectory in Figure 1b). In addition, the particle dynamics, including the acceleration, dispersion, and distribution, were investigated in this study under different particle parameters, including the Stokes number, density ratio, and releasing locations. These findings are expected to advance the state-of-the-art in mixing and dispersion of particles in stratified turbulence, introducing an efficient numerical framework for the solution of the fluid-particle interaction in a wall-bounded stratified flow.

Figure 1: (a) stratified turbulence structure; trajectories of the particle in (b) the channel core and (c) the near-wall region.

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FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION OF A CYLINDER IN A STRATIFIED FLUID

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Topics: Miscible stratified fluid, stratified wake

Key words: Stratified wake, fluid-structure interactions, Vortex Induced Vibrations, galloping

Abstract:

The influence of stratification on bluff body wakes has been studied in many different configurations. This physical situation is indeed of importance in geophysics since most geophysical fluids such as oceans and the atmosphere have stratified layers. However, fluid-structure interactions such as Vortex Induced Vibration (VIV) have only been studied in homogeneous fluids (see for example the review of Williamson and Gortvaradhan 2004 [1]). VIV is a structure oscillation which occurs, for example, when a spring mounted cylinder is submitted to a horizontal flow and that the vortex shedding frequency is close to the structure natural frequency. This is a crucial problem in the design of civil engineering structures such as bridges or marine cables because this resonance phenomenon could lead to the breaking of the structure if the induced motion is too large.

The goal of this study is to characterize the influence of a continuous stratification on this kind of system. The classical experiment of a spring-mounted cylinder is adapted to the case of a stratified fluid, characterized by its Brünt-Väisälä frequency N . A towing tank is filled with stratified salted water and cylinders of diameter D are towed horizontally at a velocity U using flat blade-shaped arms of length L (see figure 1 (a)). These arms are free to rotate around their ends thanks to ball bearings, thus allowing vertical displacement of the cylinder.

Figure 1. (a) Basic sketch of the experimental setup. (b) Vertical position of the cylinder in a homogeneous fluid (red stars) and in a stratified fluid with $Fr = 9.25$ (blue stars). Here, $L/D = 3.75$ and $Re = 6361$.

The results show that oscillations caused by a coupling between a structure and a flow also occur in a stratified fluid and that their amplitude can be larger (more than a factor 10) in the stratified case than in the homogeneous case (figure 1 (b)). By varying the main parameters D , L and U , the important non-dimensional parameters $Re=UL/\nu$ (ν being the kinematic viscosity), $Fr=U/ND$ and L/D are explored. A compilation of measures in all these cases shows the existence of two oscillations modes. The first one, interpreted as a VIV mode, has frequencies higher than N , is mainly observed for Froude larger than 3, and is favoured by low L/D ratio. The second one, interpreted as a galloping mode, has low frequencies of order $0.25N$, is localized at small Fr below 3, and is favoured by a large L/D ratio.

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REDUCING THE FORCES OF WATER ENTRY

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Topic(s): other

Key words: water entry; fluid impact; force reduction

Abstract:

Children and adults often ask us the question, “If I jump from a bridge into water can I throw an object at the water before I land and reduce the impact force?” We tested this theory by dropping two spheres, axially aligned but distance separated, into a quiescent pool of water [1]. The first sphere creates a cavity through which the second sphere enters (Figure 1b). We show that the high peak force at the first few moments of impact can be dramatically reduced under the right conditions. We identify four distinct modes of altered free surface conditions for the upper sphere. In general, the upper sphere experiences a lowered acceleration (as much as 80%) but the reduction is dependent on the spacing of the two spheres (Figure 1c). In addition, we test this theory by dropping a sphere into the water surrounded by a jet of fluid and find we also get a force reduction [2]. Further, we play with objects in the wake of the sphere cavity to see if we can also reduce the force oscillations that the sphere experiences after entry and potentially reduce the acoustic signature. The success of these experiments is directly related to the physical understanding that has grown especially in the last decade.

Figure 1: a) water entry of a single sphere 50 mm diameter at 3.75 m/s. b) water entry of a two spheres. The upper sphere 50 mm diameter at 3.75 m/s falls into a cavity created by an axially aligned sphere falling below it 32 mm diameter at 3.45 m/s. c) a comparison of the forces experienced by the on board accelerometer in a) and the upper sphere in b) shows a significant reduction in the initial impact force, and an oscillating force in b) not experienced by a).

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Generation of impulse waves by a granular flow

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Topic(s): Particles, bubbles, immiscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Granular flow, impulse waves, landslide, tsunami.

Abstract:

During the immersion of a dry granular medium into water, many phenomena can occur, whose physical description proves to be very complex despite numerous studies. Describing the deformation of the free surface in addition to the dry to wet transition of a granular flow is particularly challenging. This physical process can be directly related to the generation of impulse waves by subaerial landslides [1, 2]. Although most tsunamis are of tectonic origin, waves generated by landslides can be locally more dangerous than earthquake-generated tsunamis [3].

In this context, the presented study aims at a better understanding of the interaction between the landslide and the generated waves. A laboratory model is used consisting of a 2m long chute of varying slope angle ending in a 4m long water tank. More specifically, the landslide is modelled by a monodisperse granular flow of 1mm spherical glass beads. A picture of the experiment is represented in Figure 1. The evolution of the slide's dynamic during the crossing of the air/water interface as well as the spatio-temporal structure of the induced wave are studied as a function of the characteristics of the impacting granular flow.

Figure 1: Picture of the granular flow penetrating water.

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Dimples, jets and drops from capillary-gravity waves at a density interface

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Key words: Drops, bubbles, others

Abstract: On a windy day, bubbles entrained into the upper layer of the ocean due to wave-breaking, burst when they reach the air-sea interface. The collapse of the resulting air cavity gives rise to a jet shooting up from the trough of the cavity [1, 2]. These jets eject droplets from their tip which play a crucial role in the generation of sea-spray aerosols [3]. The mechanism of this jetting is an active area of research [4, 5, 6]. We have recently shown [7, 8, 9] using numerical simulations that such jets can also be obtained from free oscillations of an interface (separating two immiscible fluids of disparate density and viscosity) deformed initially as a Bessel mode i.e. $\hat{\eta}(\hat{r}, 0) = \hat{a}_0 J_0\left(\frac{l_q}{\hat{R}_0} \hat{r}\right)$ in a container of radius \hat{R}_0 (fig. 1a). For moderate to large values of $\epsilon \equiv \hat{a}_0 l_q / \hat{R}_0$, jetting and droplet ejection are observed at the symmetry axis (fig. 1b). Here, we study the mechanics of these jets using weakly nonlinear theory ($\epsilon < 1$ as small parameter and inviscid, irrotational approximation) and compare with numerical simulations of Euler's equation with gravity and surface tension [10]. The *weakly nonlinear* initial value problem is solved upto $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ including gravity and surface tension and predicts that [11]

$$\frac{\hat{\eta}(r, t) l_q}{\hat{R}_0} = \epsilon \cos(\omega_q t) J_0(r) + \epsilon^2 \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left[A^{(j)} + B^{(j)} \cos(2\omega_q t) + C^{(j)} \cos(\omega_j t) \right] J_0\left(\frac{l_j}{l_q} r\right) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3), \quad q \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (1)$$

with scaled variables $r \equiv \frac{l_q \hat{r}}{\hat{R}_0}$, $t \equiv \left(\frac{g l_q}{\hat{R}_0}\right)^{1/2} \hat{t}$. Here $\{l_j\}$ are the zeros of the Bessel function $J_1(\cdot)$ and $\omega_{(\cdot)}$ represents the nonlinear modal frequency. The coefficients $A^{(j)}, B^{(j)}, C^{(j)}$ satisfy $A^{(j)} + B^{(j)} + C^{(j)} = 0 \forall j \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. These and the (scaled) frequencies ω_j in eqn. 1 have lengthy expressions [11]. The weakly nonlinear analysis predicts that energy injected into a single mode at $t = 0$ is redistributed via nonlinearity into a countably infinite set of modes. Shown in figs. 1c and 1d are jets near their maximum height (numerical simulations). It is seen that expression 1 describes the jet shape well. Note that for $\epsilon = 1.2$ in fig. 1d the agreement is quite good, despite ϵ being outside the validity range of theory. Some recent results for similar jet formation from pure capillary waves and their self-similar evolution in the strongly nonlinear regime [12] will be presented at the meeting.¹

(a) Initial condition ($t = 0$). Water (red) and air (blue)

(b) Jetting and droplet formation at $\epsilon = 1.8$, axisymmetric DNS [10], also see supplementary video.

(c) Comparison of DNS [10] with $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$ and $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ theory, $\epsilon = 0.7$. Dashed line \rightarrow Max. initial perturbation height

(d) Comparison of DNS [10] with $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$ and $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ theory, $\epsilon = 1.2$. Dashed line \rightarrow Max. initial perturbation height

¹We acknowledge DST-SERB grants # EMR/2016/000830, #CRG/2020/003707 and #MTR/2019/001240 for financial support.

> **Museum visit at 18 h 30 and Gala dinner at 20 h 00**
76 Allée Charles de Fitte, 31300 Toulouse

Going to ABATTOIRS

Bus 31 (ile du ramier) at 18h16

Bus 31 (ile du ramier) at 18h33

30min walking from IMFT

18 h 30 Welcome to Museum

18 h 40 First exhibition visit

19h 15 Second exhibition visit

20 h 00 Gala dinner

18 h 40 - The Participatory Exhibition

Les Abattoirs, Musée - Frac Occitanie Toulouse open a part of their collections to you

For the first time, Les Abattoirs are offering the public the opportunity to choose the works that make up the exhibition. A vote, open from December 20, 2021 to January 10, 2022, is done directly at Les Abattoirs or online on a dedicated website.

Les Abattoirs opened in 2000. For this establishment dedicated to modern and contemporary art, works from different collections have been brought together. In addition to the expected creations - paintings, sculptures, videos, photographs, drawings, prints - the storage rooms are full of curiosities such as a bed, a caravan, the protocol of a decomposing work, birthing chairs, or oil cans. The collections constitute our common heritage and a narrative of our recent history. The writing of this history is renewed and refined through annual acquisitions, donations, deposits, but also rediscoveries, restorations, exhibitions, and the gaze of artists, professionals and visitors, which make it a living and meaningful material.

62 works are offered to the public from a collection of approximately 3,880 works and objects of all origins. They were selected according to different criteria:

The availability of the work

A work of art can circulate a lot: the more famous it is, the more it can be requested, loaned, exhibited, which reduces its availability. Our activity linked to the Regional Contemporary Art Fund (Frac) draws from the collections to propose numerous exhibitions in the region, in places as diverse as schools, retirement home, a detention center... Museums, art centers, libraries and cultural and/or public institutions can also ask us for one or more works for a thematic

or monographic exhibition.

The Abattoirs themselves regularly loan works from other museums, galleries or private collectors.

The state of conservation of the work
Some works are very fragile because of the materials used in their conception. Their conservation helps to preserve the memory of an artist or an artistic movement, for example, and is one of the main missions of a museum.

Parity

The history of collections means that in most museums, the share of works by male artists is greater. For several years now, the Abattoirs have been significantly enriching their collections with works by women artists. This selection attempts to reflect the desire to present exhibitions to the public that respect parity in artistic creation as much as possible.

In all, 585 people voted, mostly online. The average age of the voters is 45 years. They live mainly in the Occitanie region and Toulouse but other regions and large cities are represented such as Paris and its region, Bordeaux, Chartres, Le Mans, Lille, Lyon, Nantes and, abroad, Casablanca and Milan.

Taking into account the exhibition space and the size of the works, the first 18 will be presented in the 1st and 2nd basements of the Abattoirs.

19 h 15 - And now the space!

The collection of L'Observatoire de l'Espace du Cnes

From the village of Esquièze-Sère, we can see the Pic du Midi de Bigorre, a regional monument and symbol of space research by the observatory that sits at its summit. After the inaugural exhibition «Lever de rideau» in 2021, Le HANG-ART associates again with Les Abattoirs, Museum - Frac Occitanie Toulouse and it is quite naturally the subject of Space which imposes itself as local heritage and contemporary stake

Infinite, unknown, modernity or mysticism are the words that inspire the evocation of Space. This hostile and fascinating environment never ceases to inspire artists through their works and books. Since 2014, L'Observatoire de l'Espace du Cnes supports contemporary plastic creation by commissioning works from artists. These works are then deposited at Les Abattoirs for dissemination.

Et maintenant l'espace ! (And now the space!) mixes works from the collection of Les Abattoirs and L'Observatoire de l'Espace du Cnes, modern and current works. Paintings, videos, installations, photographs are mixed and deliver a curious look on the space universe from the 1980s to today. A selection of artist's books summoning the imagery of space is also presented.

With: Alexandru-Petru Badelita, Sylvie Bonnot, Angela Buloch, Raphaël Dallaporta, Ferran García Sevilla, Ludger Gerdes, Eduardo Kac, Loïc Pantaly, Bruno Petremann, Yvonne Vaar

> Wednesday, July 6th

9h00	T17 - Zhang J.- (Hybrid session)
9h30	T18 - Fouxon - (Hybrid session)
10h00	Plenary Talk #5 - Hanazaki - (Hybrid session)
10h45	Break
11h15	T19 - Patibandla
11h45	T20 - Dabiri
12h15	T22 - Mercier
12h45	Lunch
14h15	Plenary Talk #6 - Prairie
15h00	T22 - McLaughlin
15h30	T23 - Mrokowska - (Hybrid session)
16h00	Break
16h30	T24 - Mingotti - (Hybrid session)
17h00	Plenary Talk #7 - Blanchette - (Hybrid session)
17h45	closing discussions
18h45	end

Jet instability of a vertically moving sphere in a highly stratified fluid

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Topic(s): particles.

Key words: settling particle, stratified flow, jet instability, Brünt-Väisälä frequency

Abstract:

A series of 3D direct numerical simulations were carried out to study the flow past a sphere of radius a translating vertically at speed U in a stratified fluid in which density varies linearly with depth. The relevant parameters are the Reynolds number $Re = aU/\nu$, the Froude number $Fr = U/Na$ and the Prandtl (or Schmidt) number $Pr = \nu/\kappa$, where ν is the kinematic viscosity, κ is the molecular diffusivity of the stratifying agent, and N is the Brünt-Väisälä frequency characterizing the oscillations due to the prescribed density gradient. We solve the problem using the in-house JADIM Navier-Stokes solver which was recently applied to study transitional wakes past bodies settling in moderate-to-highly stratified fluids under the Boussinesq approximation [1] over a large range of parameters. Here we focus on the specific regime corresponding to highly stratified flow ($Fr < 0.3$), when the jet developing in the wake of a sphere becomes unstable, as already observed experimentally [2, 3]. Although the transition between stable and unstable jets in the wake is well identified, corresponding to ratios Fr/Re smaller than a threshold value, different typologies of unstable jets have been observed, and the mechanisms at stake remain uncertain.

To investigate this problem, we performed 3D numerical simulations with very strongly stratified fluid, down to values for the Froude number as low as $Fr = 0.05$. Very dense non-uniform grid distributions were used to capture the thin density boundary layer whose thickness δ close to the sphere is $\delta/a \sim 1/\sqrt{RePr} \approx 0.0025$ with $Re = 100$ and $Pr = 700$, and to resolve the large density variations within the jet region [3]. The snapshot of the jet velocity and density disturbance corresponding to $Re = 100$, $Pr = 700$ and $Fr = 0.05$ in Fig. 1(a) reveals a clear asymmetry in the near wake due to the jet oscillation. By tracking the development of the azimuthal component of the kinetic energy $E_k(\phi)$, shown in Fig. 1(b), we follow the growth of the jet instability. The x -component of the transverse force coefficient given in Fig. 1(c) reveals a periodic oscillation around zero due to the jet instability. As revealed by the Fourier transform in Fig. 1(d), this oscillation is dominated by a frequency $f = 3.6$ Hz, close to the Brünt-Väisälä frequency $f_{BV} = N/2\pi = 3.18$ Hz. This is a signature of a swirling or pulsating nature of the jet that we will discuss more in terms of local buoyancy perturbations and internal waves radiation. Indeed, a closer look at the early stage of the instability ($t < 10$ s) reveals that the flow field at the rear of the jet fluctuates periodically in connection with the internal waves radiated in the wake. We will discuss in further detail how these observations evolve with parameters $Re \in [25, 100]$, $Pr \in [7, 700]$, and $Fr \in [0.05, 0.1]$.

Figure 1: Jet instability of a highly stratified flows past a sphere corresponding to $Re = 100$, $Pr = 700$ and $Fr = 0.05$.

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Sedimentation of a small sphere in stratified fluid

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Topic: particles.

Key words: sedimentation, stratified fluid, drag, integral equation.

Abstract:

We report an extensive theoretical and numerical study of gravitational settling of small particles in a stratified fluid at rest. The particle motion creates a flow that advects the stratified agent, which in turn impacts the velocity by buoyancy. A peculiar insulating flow also exists when a particle and fluid at infinity are at rest, screening the particle from the outside gradients. We derive an integral representation for the linear coupled flow that holds at low Reynolds and Peclet numbers. The representation demonstrates that the far flow contains a previously unnoticed term that is produced by the thermal component of the fundamental solution. We obtain nontrivial symmetry relations that constitute a form of the Onsager reciprocal relations. Stratification is a singular perturbation: however small it is, far from the particle the flow is fast decaying and does not obey the slow power-law decay of the Stokes flow at zero stratification. We derive the enhancement of the drag force due to the stratification by adopting the integral equation on the surface traction. This allows to find the force directly, circumventing finding the flow whose calculation demands the matched asymptotic expansions that complicated previous studies. In this way we are able to extend the domain of validity of the drag formula by orders of magnitude. We confirm the predictions by numerical simulations at low Reynolds numbers. We also performed simulations for a range of nonsmall Reynolds numbers where the flow is nonlinear, but the Reynolds number is not too large. The considered range of parameters demonstrates that inclusion of stratification might be necessary for correct prediction of the sedimentation velocity of plankton particles and small organic particles of marine snow. We provide the settling velocity of *Volvox* as an example. We sum up our observations by deriving an empirical fitting formula for the drag coefficient. Finally, we discuss the observability of the insulating flow around a floating body [1].

Figure 1: Drag enhancement as a function of Rayleigh number Ra for Prandtl numbers 0.72 at $Re = 0.01$ compared with our theoretical prediction, and equation from Candelier et al. [2] in log-linear scales. Simulation data by Yick et al. [3] and Zhang et al. [4] are included for comparison.

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Jets and wakes of a sphere moving vertically in a stratified fluid

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids

Key words: jet, internal wave

Abstract:

When an obstacle moves in homogeneous fluids, we observe a downstream wake. When an obstacle moves vertically in stratified fluids, we still observe a wake under weak stratification, but it turns into a ‘jet’ under strong stratification. In this study, we consider a sphere moving vertically in linearly stratified fluids, and the results of water-tank experiments and numerical simulations will be demonstrated. The structures of jets and wakes change significantly with the Froude number Fr and the Reynolds number Re (figure 1, [1]) which are defined by $Fr = W/Na$ and $Re = 2Wa/\nu$, where W is the sphere velocity, N is the buoyancy frequency, a is the sphere radius and ν is the dynamic viscosity of fluid. We will consider the generation mechanisms of typical flow structures, including the thin jet with a ‘bell-shaped structure’ which appears under strong stratification ($Fr \sim 0.3$, $Re \sim 200$) and the periodically generated ‘knot’ which appears under moderate parameter values ($Fr \sim 10$, $Re \sim 500$). We also consider a severely stratified case ($Fr \lesssim 0.1$) in which the originally axisymmetric thin jet becomes unstable [2].

Figure 1: Dye visualisation of jets or wakes generated by a sphere moving vertically in stratified fluids. (a) $Re=230$, $Fr=0.30$; (b) $Re=1189$, $Fr=1.55$; (c) $Re=3101$, $Fr=4.17$. Reproduced from Hanazaki, Kashimoto & Okamura (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112009990498>.

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Fluid drift of a sphere settling in a stratified medium

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Topic(s): particles, immiscible stratified fluids.

Key words: Darwin drift, settling sphere, biogenic mixing

Abstract:

A biogenic source for mixing of the oceans has been actively debated in the recent literature [1,2,3]. Central to the biogenic mixing hypothesis is the persistent drift (the so-called Darwin drift) of fluid parcels, induced by the vertical motion of passive particles (marine snow) in a viscous stratified ambient [2]. However, the existence of such a drift has been countered based on the presence of an ambient stable stratification in the oceans (acting to inhibit vertical fluid motion) and the consideration of active swimmers (that have weaker velocity disturbance fields). In this context, both early [4], and recent [5-8] works have studied the disturbance fields generated by a translating particle, on large length scales, in the weak and strong advection limits, and in the absence of inertia. We extend the recent study of Varanasi and Subramanian [8], of the velocity and density disturbance fields around a translating particle, in the strong advection limit, to much larger length scales. The resulting flow field is remarkably complicated, being characterized by three different length scales: (i) a primary screening length of $O(aRi_v^{-\frac{1}{3}})$ on which stratification forces assume significance, leading to a buoyant reverse jet behind the particle and largely horizontal motion elsewhere; (ii) a secondary screening length of $O(aRi_v^{-\frac{1}{3}}\beta_\infty^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ on which diffusive forces begin to smear out the reverse jet; and (iii) a tertiary screening length of $O(aRi_v^{-\frac{1}{3}}\beta_\infty^{-\frac{1}{2}}\ln\beta_\infty^{-3})$ where fore-aft symmetry of the flow-field is eventually restored. Here, a is the sphere radius, Ri_v is the viscous Richardson number characterizing the relative importance of viscous and buoyancy forces, and $\beta_\infty = Ri_v^{\frac{1}{3}}/Pe$ is a measure of diffusive effects; Pe is the Peclet number with $\beta_\infty \rightarrow 0 (Pe \rightarrow \infty)$ denoting the strong advection limit. Further, we thoroughly investigate the Darwin drift displacements and drift volume over a wide range of Ri_v . Consistent with scaling arguments in Varanasi and Subramanian [8], the upstream and downstream components of the drift volume scale as $O(a^3 Ri_v^{-2/3})$ for $Ri_v, \beta_\infty \rightarrow 0$. Interestingly, however, the total drift volume is anomalously small, exhibiting a different scaling behavior for small Ri_v .

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MIXING BY A SWARM OF RISING BUBBLES IN A STRATIFIED FLUID

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Topic(s): bubbles, miscible stratified fluids

Key words: Mixing, bubble swarm, stratified fluid

Abstract:

Direct numerical simulations of up to 146 bubbles rising in unbounded stratified fluids using finite-volume/front-tracking method are performed. Both the bubble dynamics and destratification effects caused by the bubble motion are analyzed. The importance of bubble deformability and bubble Reynolds numbers on the induced background mixing are studied by varying the Eotvos number and Reynolds number. Highly deformable, high Reynolds number bubbles undergo path instabilities and give rise to higher levels of mixing. Liquid and bubble velocity fluctuations and pseudo-turbulence caused by the bubble motion are examined and are seen to play an important role in mixing statistics. An increase in turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) levels with void fraction is noted. TKE levels are seen to decrease slightly as the stratification strength is increased, indicating increasing stability and resistance to destratification. Regardless of the stratification strength, a kinetic energy spectrum slope value between -3 and -3.25 is reported depending on Reynolds number. The dependence of mixing parameters on the void-fraction of bubbles and stratification strength of the liquid is also presented. An increase in buoyancy flux across pycnoclines is observed as void fraction increases. A similar increase in vertical mass flux is observed for a decrease in stratification strength. The bubble dispersion and wake flow patterns are seen to strongly influence mixing properties.

Figure 1: Temperature stratification at $Fr = 14.1$, $Re = 100$, and (a) $Eo = 1.55$, (b) $Eo = 4.95$.

Mixing induced by settling objects in a stratified fluid

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids.

Key words: cluster of particles, sedimentation, mixing.

Abstract:

The influence of vertically moving objects on the mixing of a stratified fluid is of interest for various problems in industrial or environmental applications. For instance, the destruction of a stratification in water basins or lakes is often realized by bubble plumes [1]; the mixing induced by particles with finite thermal capacity (heat carriers) settling in thermally-stratified basin [2] is of importance for atmospheric and volcanic sciences; or the biogenic contribution to ocean mixing is actively debated [3, 4]. On this last topic, another effect has been more recently investigated, when the collective motion of many solid particles alter the background stratification and induce mixing of the stratified fluid. Recent work on motile organisms (active particles) has shown the importance of collective effects on local mixing [5].

The goal of this research project is to investigate the mixing induced by a cluster of settling solid objects in a linearly stratified fluid. We compare these results with the case of an isolated object.

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of the experimental setup. (b) Density field $\rho(x, z, t)$ at some instant, in the visualisation frame (center region indicated in a). (c) Available potential energy $E_a(t)$ in the visualisation window as a function of time ($Nt = 0$ when the last object leaves the window). (d) Irreversible relative change in potential energy η after settling of N_p spheres.

As illustrated in Fig.1 (a), we let N_p spheres or cylinders fall in a linearly salt-stratified tank, with $N_p \in [1, 54]$. We follow the evolution of the background stratification $\rho(x, z, t)$ in the center of the tank, by measuring dye concentration variation using a light-attenuation technique, thanks to the y -dimension of the tank being very narrow ($36 \times 6 \times 75 \text{ cm}^3$). An example is given in Fig.1 (b) where the yellow circles indicate the settling spheres. From the density measurements, we can follow the energetic transfer from the particles to the fluid using the concept of available potential energy E_a as discussed in [6], and shown in Fig.1(c). Irreversible mixing is also estimated by comparing the rate of change in potential energy, noted by η , and illustrated in Fig.1(d). We will discuss the evolution of η with N_p and with the volume displaced by each type of object (sphere vs. cylinder), for different values of the Reynolds and Froude numbers.

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Delayed settling of marine aggregates at sharp density gradients and implications for the ocean carbon cycle

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids

Key words: marine snow, aggregates, thin layers, carbon cycle

Abstract:

Marine snow aggregates, which form in the surface ocean from phytoplankton, fecal pellets, and other organic and inorganic matter, play an important role in the ocean's carbon cycle. These particles often dominate the sinking of particulate carbon from the surface ocean to the deep ocean, where it can be removed from the pool of actively cycled carbon for 1000 years or more. In addition, marine snow aggregates act as hot spots for bacterial activity and zooplankton feeding, thus constituting an integral part of marine food webs. Despite the importance of marine aggregates to fundamental processes in the ocean, there is still a lot we do not know about their settling dynamics since they are difficult to sample directly with traditional methods (nets and bottles) and because their complicated fractal geometry and porosity makes them difficult to model.

In this keynote lecture, I will give an overview of work on the delayed settling of marine aggregates as they pass through sharp density transitions. I will show evidence from laboratory experiments [1] that natural lab-formed marine aggregates do substantially decrease their settling velocity at sharp density gradients (Fig. 1) and discuss biological and physical factors that can affect this behavior [2]. Then, I will show how a constant flux of aggregates demonstrating this delayed settling behavior at a set depth will result in the formation of layers, providing evidence from both a mathematical model [3] and field observations [4]. The presence of these aggregate layers have important implications for carbon cycling in the ocean since they can affect both bacterial activity and zooplankton behavior and feeding. Lastly, I will describe directions for future work and potential areas for interdisciplinary collaborations.

Figure 1: A sequence of images from an experimental study (Prairie et al. 2013) showing the delayed settling behavior of a marine aggregate as it passes through a sharp density gradient (dotted yellow line). Time stamps are shown in red in s.

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A first-principle mechanism for particulate aggregation and self-assembly in stratified fluids

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Topic(s): (particles, miscible stratified fluids).

Key words: Self-assembly, particle aggregation

Abstract:

An extremely broad and important class of phenomena in nature involves the settling and aggregation of matter under gravitation in fluid systems. Here, we observe and model mathematically an unexpected fundamental mechanism by which particles suspended within stratification may self-assemble and form large aggregates without adhesion. This phenomenon arises through a complex interplay involving solute diffusion, impermeable boundaries, and aggregate geometry, which produces toroidal flows. We show that these flows yield attractive horizontal forces between particles at the same heights. We observe that many particles demonstrate a collective motion revealing a system which appears to solve jigsaw-like puzzles on its way to organizing into a large scale disc-like shape, with the effective force increasing as the collective disc radius grows. Control experiments isolate the individual dynamics, which are quantitatively predicted by simulations. Numerical force calculations with two spheres are used to build many-body simulations which capture observed features of self-assembly. Mathematically exact solutions are presented in the low Reynolds and low Peclet limits for a host of different boundary conditions.

Figure 1: Top: Top view montage showing particles self-assembling in stratified fluids. Bottom: Toroidal flow structures from side for single oblate spheroid, numerics (left), PIV (right).

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Dynamics of disk settling in two-layered liquid with non-linear density transition

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Topic(s): particles, miscible stratified fluids

Key words: disk, density transition, settling behaviour, wake, pycnocline

Abstract:

Settling of individual particles in low and moderate Re number regimes is a significant mechanism of particulate matter transport in ocean, seas, and lakes which are very often stratified due to vertical gradient of salinity and/or temperature. Experimental and numerical studies on settling of spherical and porous particles through background density gradients have revealed that particles experience non-monotonous settling velocity. However, settling behaviour of non-spherical particles descending through stratified ambient liquid has not been well explored yet. Only recently it has been demonstrated that settling dynamics of spheroids is characterised by stratification-induced reorientations as the effect of buoyancy-induced torques [1, 2]. Non-spherical particles exhibit much more complex settling dynamics than spherical counterparts due to additional physical mechanisms which has not been yet fully recognised, which is the motivation of study presented herein.

Figure 1: Variation of non-dimensional settling velocity of individual disk with depth (four repetitions of the same experiment). Particles settle from left to right. Location of characteristic velocities $u_{\min 1}$, $u_{\min 2}$ and the onset of settling phases: II, III, and IV are shown. Velocity is non-dimensionalized by terminal settling velocity in upper layer, U_{ul} , and particle position by disk diameter, d , z_0 is position of density interface, N is buoyancy frequency. For definitions please refer to [3, 4].

Here I present the selected results of experimental studies on the settling of disks through a two-layer water column with non-linear density transition [3, 4]. The aim was to quantify the effect of stratification characteristics and disk geometric anisotropy on (1) settling velocity and reorientation pattern of a disk (2) hydrodynamic interactions between a disk and a wake and (3) the horizontal drift of disk. Disks made of ABS varying in diameters (2 mm and 3 mm) and thickness (0.44 mm and 0.05 mm) were used. Settling experiments were carried out in a tank filled with two-layered liquid column formed by aqueous salt solutions. Descent of particles was recorded using cameras to retrieve 2D and 3D particle position and trajectory. Measurements confirmed the existence of five phases of settling in non-linear density transition characterised by a sequence of reorientations and the presence of two local minimum settling velocities shown in Fig. 1. Critical parameters for settling dynamics were quantified and the displacement of a disk in a horizontal plane during the change of spatial orientation was assessed. Moreover, a unique bell-shaped flow structure was observed behind a thick disk, and physical mechanism of various forms of wakes were explained. These findings address the basic mechanisms of particle settling which may help understand microscale physics of marine particles and improve the estimation of sedimentation processes.

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PARTICLE-LADEN PLUMES IN THE OCEAN: IMPLICATIONS FOR DEEP-SEA MINING

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Topic: Particle-laden plumes in a stratified ambient.

Key words: Particles, sedimentation, plume, turbulence, current.

Abstract:

The demand for raw materials including copper, cobalt and magnesium is set to soar during the energy transition. Deep-sea mining operations are being developed to mine these resources from the Pacific seafloor. Large amounts of waste sediment will be produced as a result of these operations and discharged at sea, resulting in dense sediment-laden plumes descending through the water column. This may lead to significant environmental impact associated with the plume water and/or the particles in the discharge.

We present new laboratory experiments which aim to investigate the dynamics of such particle-laden plumes descending through a stratified ambient. We show that in a quiescent environment (figure 1a), the particle-laden fluid descends vertically until it is arrested by the stratification. An intrusion is formed at the neutral buoyancy height, where the particles separate from the plume fluid and settle out. Our experiments show that the depth at which the plume fluid intrudes following particle separation may differ significantly from that of an intruding single-phase plume of identical buoyancy flux. We also show that the particles sediment at their fall speed through the fluid underneath the intrusion, leading to negligible vertical transport of fluid in the water column.

In the ocean, the dynamics of the plume flow may be affected by marine currents. We carried out a second series of experiments, in which a particle-laden plume descended through an ambient with a cross-flow (figure 1b). Here, the particle-fluid mixture initially moves as one, but as the plume descends, the particles gradually begin to accumulate at the base of the flow and settle out. In a stratified ambient, the stratification may arrest the plume prior to significant particle sedimentation, and in this case, the plume tends to spread downstream at the level of neutral buoyancy, where particle sedimentation proceeds (see figure 1b).

The experiments highlight the range of flow processes which may influence the dispersion and sedimentation of particles in deep-sea mining plumes, depending on the initial flux and concentration of particles in the plume, the ambient density and the particle fall speed.

Figure 1: Particle-laden plumes descending through (a) a quiescent stratified ambient and (b) a cross-flow.

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Modeling and Simulations of Marine Aggregates

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Topic(s): Particles, miscible stratified fluids.

Keywords: Marine aggregates, porous particles, stratification, drag, fractal particles.

Abstract:

Marine aggregates play an important role in transporting carbon from the surface ocean to the deep ocean. Investigations of their settling rates is critical to understand the ecological impact of these particles. Here, we present first a numerical study of the settling of a porous sphere, modeling marine aggregates, in a density-stratified ambient fluid. Two main effects cause the particle to slow down as it enters a density gradient (Fig. 1a): lighter fluid within the particle and distortion of the flow around the sphere by the ambient stratification. We quantify in [1] the retention time, during which the sphere is nearly at rest as a function of the Reynolds, Péclet, and Darcy numbers, as well as the thickness of the transition layer and the ratio of the density difference between the lower and upper fluid layers to the density difference between the particle and the upper layer.

Figure 1: a) Concentration field around a porous sphere settling in an ambient stratification.
b) Sample streamlines around a fractal aggregate.

We then move to improve our model by accounting for the complicated shapes of marine aggregates. Naturally occurring marine aggregates are very irregular, having in fact been shown to have a fractal structure (Fig. 1b). We therefore study numerically the fluid forces acting on aggregates formed by the diffusion-limited aggregation of cubic particles [2]. The flow around the aggregates and the resulting stresses on its surface are computed in the limit of zero Reynolds number using a boundary integral method. We characterize the drag of translation flows, the torque of rotational flows, and the straining force of extensional flows acting on aggregates as a function of their size and mode of formation. We determine that the force and torque are best characterized using the gyration radius of the aggregates, and the straining force is better characterized by the maximal radius.

Lastly, we revisit the formation mechanism of marine aggregates to incorporate the results obtained on their drag and torque. We study numerically the formation of aggregates using a Brownian dynamics model where the resistivity of each aggregate depends on its size. We investigate the growth rate and resulting fractal dimension of aggregates and quantify the impact of increased resistivity, rotation, and settling.

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